

Figure 1 – Representative brightfield (greyscale) and fluorescent images of propidium iodide (red) of single spheres of HSJD-DIPG-007 cells. After three days of undisturbed growth, spheres were treated with 1:1000 propidium iodide and either fed with fresh medium or treated with matrigel. Propidium iodide indicates development of a necrotic core in spheres above 500µm in diameter. Scale bars are 500µm and all images are presented at the same scale.